

Synthesis, spectral and antimicrobial evaluation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes of *N*-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-*N*-[(3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]-oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine

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Abstract : A novel series of metal complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} of *N*-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-*N*-[(3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine were synthesized and characterized by their melting point determination of recrystallized samples, running TLC for single spot, elemental analysis, molar conductance, molecular weight determination, IR, ¹H NMR, magnetic moment values, electronic spectral and thermal studies. All the synthesized compounds, viz. (3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (2), 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]-oxadiazin-2-yl)-hydrazone (3), *N*-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-*N*-[(3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine (4) and their metal complexes (5a-d) were screened for antimicrobial activities *in vitro* against Gram +ve bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram -ve bacteria (*Escherichia coli*) and two fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*. Compound 2 exhibited significant antimicrobial activity which increased in its hydrazone (3). The activity further increased in the form of its derivative (4). Although all metal complexes exhibited maximum activity against both bacteria and fungi but the metal complex of Cu^{II} was found most active.

Keywords : Synthesis, spectral, IR, NMR, electronic spectral, TGA, hydrazone, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds find a special place among pharmaceutically significant natural and synthetic compounds. The remarkable ability of heterocyclic nuclei to serve both as biomimetics and reactive pharmacophores has largely contributed to their unique value as a key moiety of numerous drugs¹. Among the heterocyclic compounds 1,3,4-oxadiazines and their fused compounds have been reported as monoamine oxidase inhibitors², antitumor³, analgesics⁴ and anticonvulsant⁵ agents. Thus, the chemistry of 1,2,4-oxadiazines and their fused compounds may be an evolving sphere for the pharmacological activity. In recent years, heterocyclic compounds, hydrazones and their metal complexes have been reported as potential antimicrobial⁶, anti-inflammatory⁷, analgesic⁷, antioxidant⁸, antitubercular⁹, antiHIV¹⁰, anticancerous¹¹ and antitumour^{12,13} agents. These versatile applications have prompted us to synthesize a new hydrazone, its derivative and metal complexes to access their biological activi-

ties *in vitro*. In continuation of our previous work¹⁴, this research paper deals with the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of a new heterocyclic compound (3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (2), 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-hydrazone (3), *N*-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-*N*-[(3-methyl-2*H*-benzo[*e*][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine (4) and their Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes (5a-d) synthesized according to the Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

All the compounds were colored and stable at room temperature. Heterocyclic compound, hydrazone and its derivative were soluble in ethanol. Metal complexes were soluble in DMF and DMSO. Physical and analytical data of compound 2, 3, 4 and 5a-d have been reported in (Table 1). The analytical data of complexes suggested their (1 : 1) M : L stoichiometry. The low molar conductance values (3.5–10 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO at room temperature sug-

Scheme 1

gested their non electrolytes nature.

IR spectra :

IR spectra of all the compounds exhibited bands in the region $3064.9\text{--}3019.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1468.0\text{--}1414.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to C-H and C=C stretching vibrations¹⁵ of aromatic rings respectively. A medium sharp intensity band in compound **2** was observed at 1703.0 cm^{-1} corresponding to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration¹⁵. This band has disappeared in the case of compound **3** and a new band at 1620.0 cm^{-1} appeared which indicates the formation of $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ linkage¹⁶. In the IR spectra of compound **4** a band at 1591.2 cm^{-1} has also observed due to

the formation of $>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ linkage¹⁶ resulted by the condensation of NH_2 group of compound **3** with $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of furfuraldehyde. In the metal complexes these bands have shifted to their lower region ($1569.9\text{--}1546.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which suggested the participation of the nitrogen atom of $>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}<$ linkage in the coordination with metal ion. In the IR spectra of compounds **2**, **3** and **4** a band in the region $1280.1\text{--}1219.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was observed which may be due to the C-O-N stretching vibrations. This band has also shifted towards the lower frequency region in all the metal complexes indicating the involvement of oxygen atom of 1,2,4-oxadiazine moiety

Table 1. Physical properties and elemental analysis data of compound **2**, **3**, **4** and **5a-d**

Compd.	Molecular formula	Colour	Elemental analyses (%) :				Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	M.P. /D.T. $\pm 2^\circ \text{ C}$
			Found (Calcd.)						
			Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen	Metal			
2	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	Shiny	71.04	4.31	10.98	–	247	92	
		brown	(71.42)	(4.76)	(11.11)	–	(252)		
3	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{ON}_4$	Greenish	67.27	5.20	21.50	–	260	110	
		black	(67.66)	(5.26)	(21.05)	–	(266)		
4	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$	Light	68.85	5.21	15.26	–	335	140	
		brown	(69.76)	(4.65)	(16.27)	–	(344)		
5a	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4).3\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{Ac})_2$	Black	49.38	5.93	8.37	9.02	10.0	583.12	305
			(50.09)	(4.87)	(9.74)	(10.24)		(574.93)	
5b	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4).3\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{Ac})_2$	Brown	49.17	3.92	9.57	9.45	3.5	585.39	250
			(50.11)	(4.87)	(9.74)	(10.21)		(574.69)	
5c	$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4).3\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{Ac})_2$	Black	50.45	5.60	8.63	9.82	4.8	568.05	265
			(49.69)	(4.83)	(9.66)	(10.96)		(579.54)	
5d	$[\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4).3\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{Ac})_2$	Shiny	48.38	4.12	8.40	10.45	8.9	570.10	290
		black	(49.53)	(4.81)	(9.63)	(11.24)		(581.39)	

in the coordination with metal ion. A medium sharp intensity band in the region 1488.0 cm^{-1} of furan breathing vibration¹⁷ has appeared in the IR spectra of compound **4** which has shifted towards higher frequency region 1526.0 – 1518.5 cm^{-1} suggesting coordination of furan ring oxygen with metal ion. The presence of coordinate water molecules within coordination sphere of all complexes is supported by the appearance of broad bands in the region 3452.6 – 3376.3 cm^{-1} and 885.1 – 831.8 cm^{-1} due to stretching and bending vibrations of -OH group respectively. IR spectra of all complexes showed two new bands in the regions 491.3 – 476.1 cm^{-1} , 539.3 – 513.5 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to M–O and M–N vibrations respectively¹⁷.

¹H NMR spectra :

¹H NMR spectral data of compounds **2**, **3** and **4** exhibited two multiplets in the range δ 6.85–6.39 and 7.70–7.41 ppm which may be due to the protons of benzo ring fused with 1,2,4-oxadiazine and phenyl ring¹⁸. A singlet at δ 7.27 ppm due to NH₂ proton¹⁹ was appeared in the spectra of compound **3**. A singlet appeared in the range δ 2.35–2.25 ppm in the spectra of compounds **2**, **3** and **4** may be due to protons of (-CH₃) group¹⁹. Compound **4** also exhibited one more multiplet and a singlet in the region at δ 7.11–6.93 ppm and a singlet at δ 7.77 ppm which could be due to protons of furyl ring and N=C–H group²⁰ respectively.

Electronic spectra and magnetic moment measurements :

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complex displayed three bands at 763.06 nm, 675.12 nm, 569.47 nm corresponding to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ respectively. These transitions as well as the measured value of the magnetic moment 4.86 BM suggested an octahedral geometry²¹ for this complex.

Ni^{II} complex exhibited three bands at 890.47 nm, 579.40 nm and 393.20 nm corresponding to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_1 (P)$ respectively which was in good agreement with its octahedral geometry²¹. Further, the magnetic moment value for this complex was found 2.96 BM which is in conformity of the above.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complex exhibited three bands at 754.71 nm, 567.44 nm and 414.76 nm corresponding to the transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry²² for this complex and is further confirmed by its observed magnetic moment value 1.83 BM.

In the electronic spectra of Zn^{II} complex, no significant bands were noticed which concludes its diamagnetic nature.

Thermal studies :

Thermogravimetric curves revealed that all complexes decompose in four steps. The complexes undergo first step decomposition with weight loss 20.60–20.15% between 96–110 °C corresponding to the weight loss of outer sphere acetate ions. The second decomposition was observed between 140–210 °C with weight loss 9.45–9.20% which could be due the loss of three coordinated water molecules of coordination sphere. The third decomposition was found between 265–380 °C corresponding to weight loss 34.36–33.80% due to loss of $C_{12}H_9O$ and N_2 moieties. After that the complexes undergo decomposition between 420–525 °C corresponding to weight loss 25.60–25.27% due to loss of remaining part of the ligand. Finally, complexes were converted into their metal oxides as end product. Thermograms of complexes have

been shown in Fig. 1.

Antimicrobial results and discussion :

A comparative study of MIC values (Table 2) indicated that compound **2** has significant antimicrobial activity against both bacteria and fungi which further increased in the form of its hydrazone (compound **3**) and its derivative compound **4**. Metal complexes were found more active against both bacteria and fungi. The increased antimicrobial activity²³ of the complexes as compared to the ligand may be due to their chelation which reduces the polarity of the metal ion by partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possibly π -electron delocalization within the whole chelate ring thus increases the lipophilicity of the complexes, causing a rapid penetration through the lipid layer of cell membrane restricting the multiplicity of the microorganism.

Fig. 1. Thermograms of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes.

Table 2. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration ($\times 10^{-3}$ mole) values of compound **2**, **3**, **4** and **5a-d**

Compd.	Bacteria		Fungi	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
2	99.2	99.2	99.2	99.2
3	93.9	93.9	93.9	93.9
4	36.3	36.3	72.6	72.6
5a	43.4	43.4	43.4	43.4
5b	21.7	21.7	43.5	43.5
5c	21.5	21.5	21.5	21.5
5d	43.0	43.0	43.0	43.0
Ciprofloxacin	18.8	18.8	–	–
Griseofulvin	–	–	17.7	17.7

Among the metal complexes, Cu^{II} complex was found most active against both bacteria and fungi. Its antibacterial activity was found very close to the activity value of ciprofloxacin (Antibiotic drug) and antifungal activity of this compound was very close to the value of griseofulvin (Antifungal drug) both taken as standard for comparison. The maximum activity of the copper complex²⁴ may be due to higher stability constant and more lipo soluble nature.

Experimental

Analytical and physical measurements : The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by running their TLC for single spot on silica gel-G plates and by repeated melting point determination of the recrystallized samples in open capillaries and was uncorrected. The microanalysis of C, H and N analyses were carried out by using micro analyzer technique on Carbo Erba micro analyzer 1108. Cobalt, nickel, copper and zinc contents in their metal complexes were estimated by their pyridine complex²⁵ formation method. Molecular weight determination of the compounds was done by cryoscopic²⁶ method. The molar conductance of complexes were measured at room temperature in 10^{-3} M solutions in DMSO by Toshniwal digital conductivity meter with a dip type cell. IR spectra were recorded in KBr in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} on Perkin-Elmer Model Rx1 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Biospin spectrometer DPX-300 MHz and electronic spectra of metal complexes were recorded on Shimadzu model (UV150-150.02) spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as calibrant. Thermogravi-

metric analyses (TGA) were recorded in a static nitrogen atmosphere with heating rate of 10 °C/min using Diamond TG/DTA analyzer.

Synthesis of N-benzoyl acetohydroxamic acid (1) : N-Benzoyl acetohydroxamic acid was synthesized by the reaction of finely powdered hydroxylamine hydrochloride, benzoyl chloride and acetyl chloride in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio as reported earlier¹⁴.

Synthesis of (3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (2) : This compound has also been synthesized by reacting 1 : 1 molar ratio of 2-aminophenol and N-benzoyl acetohydroxamic acid in absolute alcohol by the method reported¹⁴ in our previous paper.

Synthesis of 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]-oxadiazin-2-yl)-hydrazone (3) : 3-Phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-hydrazone has been synthesized by the reaction of 3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]-oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methanone (0.004 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.004 mol) in absolute alcohol by the method reported¹⁴ in our previous paper.

Synthesis of N-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-N-[(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine (4) : 1.06 g (0.004 mol) 3-phenyl-3-(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-hydrazone, dissolved in 20 ml absolute alcohol, and 0.33 ml (0.004 mol) furfuraldehyde, dissolved in 15 ml absolute alcohol, were mixed. The mixture was refluxed for 16 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature and poured onto the crushed ice. The obtained solid product was filtered and recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. Finally, it was dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Synthesis of metal complexes of N-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-N-[(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine (5a-d) : 25 ml ethanolic solution of 0.688 g (0.002 mol) *N*-(furan-2-yl)-methylene-*N*-[(3-methyl-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]oxadiazin-2-yl)-phenyl-methylene]-hydrazine was mixed with 10 ml aqueous solution (0.002 mol) of 0.498 g cobalt acetate tetrahydrate/0.497 g nickel acetate tetrahydrate/0.399 g copper acetate monohydrate/0.438 g zinc acetate dihydrate. The contents were refluxed for 3–6 h. On cooling, obtained precipitates were filtered, washed with alcohol followed by ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial studies of the synthesized compounds were screened against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (Gram -ve) and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by adopting Serial Dilution Method²⁷ in suitable nutrient medium (1.5 g peptone, 0.75 g yeast extract, 0.37 g beef extract, 0.37 g agar only for slant and 0.25 g dextrose in 250 ml distilled water for bacteria and 2.5 g peptone, 5.12 g agar only for slant and 5.0 g dextrose in 250 ml distilled water for fungi). Graded diluted solutions of the test compounds, with the micro organisms under examination using aseptic condition, were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h in case of bacteria and at 28 °C for 96 h in case of fungi in a B.O.D. incubator. The test tube having the highest dilution, i.e. lowest concentration showing no visible turbidity was chosen for the MIC value.

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References

1. R. S. Varma, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1999, **36**, 1565.
2. D. L. Trepanier, J. N. Eble and V. Sprancmanis, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 753.
3. R. M. Mohareb and E. M. Samir, *Open Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2012, **2**, 1.
4. D. L. Trepanier, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, **70(2)**, 115189; US Patent, **3**, 432, 497.
5. D. L. Trepanier and G. H. Harris, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1968, **69**, 59293; US Patent, **3**, 377, 345.
6. D. Kumar, S. Singh, N. Sharma and R. Akhtar, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India, Sect. A : Phys. Sci.*, 2012, **82**, 23.
7. M. A. A. Radwan, E. A. Ragab, N. M. Sabry and S. M. El-Shenawy, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15(11)**, 3832.
8. Q. Wang, Z.-Y. Yang, G.-F. Qi and D.-D. Qin, *Biometals*, 2009, **22**, 927.
9. L. Savini, L. Chiasserini, A. Gaeta and C. Pellerano, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **10**, 2193.
10. P. Vicini, M. I. Incerti, P. L. Colla and R. Loddo, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 1801.
11. N. Terzioglu and A. Gursoy, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **38**, 781.
12. R. M. Mohareb and A. A. Mohamed, *Molecules*, 2010, **15**, 3602.
13. A. H. Pathan and K. B. Gudasi, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2013, **22(3)**, 1504.
14. D. Kumar and Neelam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 665.
15. G. C. Bassler and R. M. Silverstein "Spectroscopic Identification of Organic Compound", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc, New York, 1967.
16. D. H. Williams and I. Fleming, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd., USA, 1996.
17. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 5th ed., John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1997.
18. Y. R. Sharma, "Elementary Organic Spectroscopy", 12th ed., S. Chand and Company Ltd., New Delhi, 2000.
19. A. M. Awadallah and N. M. El-Halabi, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 280.
20. L. M. Jackman, "Applications of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", 1st ed., Pergamon, New York, 1959.
21. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
22. A. B. P. Lever and E. Mantovani, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 40.
23. G. J. Tortora, B. R. Funke and C. L. Case, "Microbiology – An Introduction", 10th ed., Benjamin Cummings, California, 2009.
24. L. Mitu, N. Raman, A. Kriza, N. Stanica and M. Dianu, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **74(10)**, 1075.
25. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS Longman, London, 1968.
26. J. A. Dean, "Langes Hand Book of Chemistry", 15th ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1978.
27. D. F. Spooner and G. Sykes, "Methods in Microbiology", Academic Press, London, 1972.